

On Activated Charcoal. Part I.

BY SATYAPRASAD ROYCHOUDHURY.

The activation of charcoal has been ascribed to a variety of possible causes, *e.g.*, broadening of the pores, change in the structure of the surface layer, breakdown of the crystal structure (Philip, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 361; Ogawa, *Biochem. Z.*, 1925, 161, 275; *ibid.*, 1926, 172, 249; Freundlich, *Capillary Chemistry*, Eng. Ed., 1926, p. 183; Kolthoff, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1929, 46, 549; Ruff and Mautner, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1928, 46, 549). The optimum conditions have not however been correlated with any definite property of the charcoal. In fact Dubinin has observed (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 140, 81) that the order of adsorption of aliphatic acids changes with the conditions of activation. Thus the optimum condition would vary with the nature of the adsorbate (see also Ogawa *loc. cit.*). The role of substances other than carbon which may be formed during activation or may be present as impurities has recently received prominent attention. Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1031) prepared ash-free sugar charcoal and attributed the different observations of Michaelis and Rona (*Biochem. Z.*, 1919, 97, 57; *ibid.*, 1919, 94, 240) to the inorganic constituents of the ash present in their sample.

The recent works of Schilow and his co-workers (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 133, 188; *ibid.*, 1928, 136, 34; *ibid.*, 1929, 143, 41; *ibid.*, 1930, 148, 233; *ibid.*, 1930, 149, 211; *ibid.*, 1930, 150, 31; *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 107) and of Frumkin and his co-workers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1926, 158, 84; *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 141, 141, 290; *ibid.*, 1930, 147, 125; *ibid.*, 1930, 150, 421; *ibid.*, 1930, 151, 87; *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 51, 123) constitute a fundamental advance both in the technique and in the knowledge of the subject. Schilow and his co-workers emphasise the role played by oxides of carbon formed during activation. Schilow assumes the formation of two basic oxides A and B and an acidic oxide C whose stability depends on the temperature.

In explaining the different orders of adsorption Schilow and co-workers have shown that activated charcoals can be prepared from pure sugar which adsorbs (i) only an acid (hydrochloric) but not an alkali (sodium hydroxide), (ii) only an alkali but no acid, (iii) both the acid and the alkali. These results are difficult to reconcile with the theory of Frumkin (see later), according to which charcoal prepared under these conditions should function as an oxygen electrode and should adsorb acids but not alkalies. The observations of Kruyt and Kadt (*Kolloid Z.*, 1929, **77**, 44) who found that sugar charcoal activated in oxygen had a negative charge and that this sample adsorbed alkali are also against Frumkin's theory as these samples should have a positive charge and adsorb no alkali.

Frumkin explains them by assuming that these samples contain acid substances formed by activation. Kruyt and Kadt (*loc. cit.*) also found that charcoal activated in carbon dioxide had a positive charge and did not adsorb alkali. This shows that the charcoal does not always behave as an oxygen electrode in Frumkin's sense. In explaining the different orders of adsorption of aliphatic acids with the conditions of activation of charcoal observed, Dubinin (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **150**, 145, 154) considers that the size of the pores and the effective surface have to be considered in addition to the presence of such oxides. These observations are also difficult to account for on the basis of Frumkin's theory (see later). The explanation of adsorptive properties of charcoal upheld by Frumkin and his co-workers (*loc. cit.*) is very simple and attractive and rests on classical electrochemical considerations. Charcoal functions as an oxygen or hydrogen electrode in the presence of the respective gases analogous to the wellknown behaviour of platinum. There would thus exist the well known relation between the pressure of oxygen or hydrogen and the acid or alkali adsorption respectively. Frumkin in a series of fine experiments has shown that treatment with oxygen increases and treatment with hydrogen decreases the adsorption of acids—this is in qualitative agreement with his theory. Both Schilow and Frumkin however agree that the simple quantitative relationship between the adsorbed amounts of acid or alkali and amounts of gaseous oxygen and hydrogen respectively consumed during this process is not satisfied. Changes in the composition and chemical nature of the oxides postulated by Schilow or of other substances with similar properties if present in the charcoal surface would account for the qualitative agreement. On

account of the fact that charcoal when activated even in presence of hydrogen absorbs acids, Frumkin holds that the hydrogen charcoal is difficult to prepare and charcoal free from platinum behaves always as an oxygen charcoal. This is attributed to the great affinity of charcoal for oxygen. That complex oxides, as suggested by Schilow, may be present is not denied by Frumkin (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 51, 126) but it is held that the mechanism of acid adsorption is that stated above. In analogy with the wellknown case of the platinum-oxygen electrode, oxygen charcoal is assumed to have a positive charge resulting from the displacement of an electron from the surface. The hydroxyl ions formed from the union of the negatively charged oxygen ions and a molecule of water leave the surface and neutralise the hydrogen ions so that the anion (*e.g.*, chloridion of hydrochloric acid) would form a sort of chloride of carbon. Similarly charcoal containing a small percentage of platinum, which Frumkin holds acts as a hydrogen electrode in presence of hydrogen, would have a negative charge, neutralise alkali and form a 'sodium-carbon' electrolyte. The amounts of acid or alkali adsorption measure respectively the amount of oxygen or hydrogen consumed during the adsorption process. Frumkin (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 147, 145) in fact suggests that what matters is the thermodynamic potential of the oxygen in the charcoal electrode and it is immaterial in what form the oxygen is present in the charcoal. The exact function of the oxygen is however most important for a correct understanding of the mechanism of the reaction and also in deciding the correctness or otherwise of Frumkin's theory. Schilow has shown and Frumkin agrees that the curve of adsorption of acid by *outgassed* charcoal at various oxygen pressures shows a form contrary to the exponential relation postulated in this theory. Frumkin points out that the evidence leads to a saturation oxygen potential (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 150, 432). Further, on exhausting charcoal of gases at high temperature and vacuum and then introducing air, it is found that the adsorption of valerianic acid increases but the power to adsorb hydrochloric acid diminishes (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 150, 43) which is also difficult to account for from this theory. For the picture would be different according as an oxide of carbon regulates the hydroxyl-ion concentration (as for example is the case with say, mercury-mercuric oxide electrode) or the pressure of oxygen determines it. A mercury-mercurous oxide electrode would act as a hydroxyl-ion electrode even in the complete absence of oxygen (*e.g.* in nitrogen), whereas if no similar stable oxide of carbon were present, charcoal should

absorb no acid in the complete absence of gaseous oxygen. Frumkin (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 150, 435) finds however that even platinum charcoal in presence of hydrogen, which he concludes from other experiments (*Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 51, 123) behaves as a hydrogen electrode, adsorbs acids but should not do so. He explains this by assuming that an additional loose type of adsorption similar to that in an air-water interface (*i.e.* the well known Gibb's type of adsorption) manifests itself at high concentrations. There is also a negative adsorption of acids by the same charcoal at low concentration. This he refers to the adsorption of water by the charged charcoal surface. Still another type of adsorption is assumed by Frumkin in addition to the above for he (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 141, 150) finds that the adsorption of benzoic acid is the same for oxygen charcoal and hydrogen charcoal containing 2% platinum. This is remarkable as this cannot be reconciled with Frumkin's simple theory. Frumkin further points out in the first paper of the series (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, 141, 144) that his theory does not apply to the observations of Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 191 ; also Mukherjee and Basu, *ibid.*, 1926, 3, 371) and of Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2605) on hydrolytic adsorption by silicic acid, manganese oxide and other substances. This is important and shows that if definite acidic or basic oxides exist on the charcoal, they are sufficient in themselves to account for the observations. As indicated above, an insoluble film of basic oxide would act as a reversible oxygen (hydroxyl ion) electrode. There is no question of oxygen consumption or pressure of oxygen in such an equilibrium, unless the composition of the oxide varies with oxygen pressure.

Both Frumkin and Schilow have tried to correlate the electric charge of the charcoal surface with its behaviour in such adsorptive processes. In opposition to Frumkin, Schilow holds that charcoal is a negative absorbent and has a strong (preferential) adsorption of anions. It should thus be charged negatively in water as also in neutral electrolytes and the adsorption of the acid is attributed to the covering up of the anions by hydrogen ions, displaced from the solution by what he terms 'molarisation' as also through the existence of an adsorption potential of cations, analogous to the electrochemical potential series. The more positive element is supposed to displace hydrogen ions from the solution to the interface. It will be seen later that the charcoal

does not act as a negative adsorbent in Schilow's sense. To account for non-adsorption or negative adsorption of alkali, Schilow assumes that (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 133, 188) "hydroxyl ions are adsorbed out of water and out of alkali" and they in turn adsorb hydrogen ions but not alkali metal cations and a molecular adsorption occurs. With activated charcoal, however, the more it is washed with water, the more it assumes a positive charge. Further, it will be seen that there is a relationship between the charge of the surface and the adsorption of acid or alkali not contemplated in Schilow's theory. Schilow's own observation that charcoal can adsorb both acid and alkali definitely contradicts his assumption that charcoal primarily absorbs hydroxyl ions and hydrogen ions only through molarisation or displacement from solution by the more positive cation. Neither Schilow nor Frumkin has however made experiments on the charge of the charcoal surface.

That absorption of ions, hydrolytic adsorption and adsorption of electrolytes are closely correlated with the electrical charge has been shown by Mukherjee and co-workers (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 219; also, *Proceedings, Indian Science Congress*, 1929, p. 93; *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 49, 362). A theory similar in some respects to that of Mukherjee was later suggested also by Bartell and Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 992) to account for hydrolytic adsorption by charcoal. The electric charge of the charcoal surface is also of interest in relation to the work of Fromageot (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 972, 1404; *Nature*, Sept. 14, 1929) who states that charcoal adsorbs neutral molecules of acids and not ions. Phelps and Peters (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1929, A 124, 554) are also of the same opinion. Umetsu (*Biochem. Z.*, 1923, 135, 442) found that acids and alkalies have a marked effect on the electrical charge of the surface.

The exact function of substances other than carbon thus constitutes a very important point at issue.* The work of Pawlow (*Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 35, 225) is of interest in that it indicates how the presence of substances can be verified by determining the effect of mass on the adsorption. The present paper deals with (A) condition of maximum activation; (B) the effect of mass of the adsorbent; (C) purifica-

* Bhatnagar, Mathur and Kapur (*Indian J. Phys.*, 1927-28, 3, 53) hold from measurements of the magnetic susceptibility of charcoal with Fe^{++} ions adsorbed on it that chemical changes of the type postulated by Langmuir (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 1361) take place between the adsorbent and the adsorbed material.

tion of activated charcoal by washing; (D) order of adsorption of acids; (E) equivalent adsorption of ions of an acid; (F) effect of ethyl alcohol on the adsorption of acids by different samples of charcoal; (G) hydrolytic adsorption and electrical charge on the charcoal surface.

Preparation of Materials.

(1) *Animal Charcoal.*—Merck's animal charcoal was finely powdered and digested with hydrochloric and hydrofluoric acids in a platinum basin. It was next washed several times with boiling conductivity water (Miller, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 30, 1031). The electrical conductivity of the wash liquid (boiling conductivity water) offers the best test of removal of electrolytes. After boiling 15 g. of charcoal with 500 c.c. of conductivity water 20 times, the specific conductivity fell from 156×10^{-5} to 173×10^{-5} r. o. These purified samples were used for activation in an electric furnace. A closed silica tube, with a tight rubber cork fitted with glass tubes connecting with a Cenco vacuum pump and a pressure gauge, was used. After activation, the charcoal was cooled and transferred into clean stoppered Jena glass bottles. Exposure to the atmosphere was as brief as possible. The bottles were kept inside a big vacuum desiccator containing caustic soda sticks and phosphorus pentoxide. Two perforated zinc sheets were placed horizontally at some distance from each other above the desiccating agents.

(2) *Sugar Charcoal.*—Merck's extra-pure cane sugar was used and the charcoal prepared as given by Miller (*loc. cit.*). The charcoal was boiled several times with conductivity water before activation (samples J to Q).

(3) *Gelatin Charcoal.*—Merck's ordinary pure gelatin was ignited strongly in a covered silica basin in order to burn off tarry matter. It was then powdered and again ignited free from the combustible ingredients. It was purified, activated and preserved as above (samples R and S).

A. *Conditions of Maximum Activation.*

The extent of activation of animal, sugar and gelatin charcoals prepared under different conditions of temperature, duration of heating, and in contact with air (10 mm. pressure), as also in contact with dry and well-purified N_2 and CO_2 (in the case of animal and

sugar charcoal only) has been measured from the adsorption of benzoic acid (0.02 *N*) (Miller, *loc. cit.*). 50 C.c. of the electrolyte were kept in contact with the charcoal for 20 hrs. The upper liquid was separated by means of a powerful centrifuge. Baryta and phenolphthalein were used for titration.

Changes in volume due to the admixture and the adsorption of the solvent are negligible. The amounts adsorbed are given below in gram moles per gram of charcoal multiplied *thousand* times and the amount of charcoal in grams. The concentrations are in normality.

TABLE I.

Animal charcoal : activated with air : pressure-10 mm.

Sample.	Temp. (°C.).	Duration (hrs.).	Amount (g.).	Initial conc. (<i>N</i>).	Final conc. (<i>N</i>).	Amount adsorbed (g. mole/g. × 10 ³).
A	700°	4	·125	·021	·0146	2.56
			·25	·021	·01	2.2
			·5	·0196	·0021	1.75
B	600°	4	·125	·021	·0154	2.24
			·25	·021	·01	2.2
			·5	·0196	·0032	1.64
C	600°	8	·125	·021	·0142	2.72
			·25	·021	·0084	2.52
			·5	·0196	·0015	1.81
D	600°	28	·125	·0208	·0146	2.48
			·25	·0208	·0102	2.12
			·5	·0196	·0020	1.76

TABLE II.

Animal charcoal : activated with carbon dioxide : atmospheric pressure.

Sample.	Temp. (°C.).	Duration (hrs.).	Amount (g.).	Initial conc. (<i>N</i>).	Final conc. (<i>N</i>).	Amount adsorbed (g. mole/g. × 10 ³).
E	600°	4	·125	·0208	·0142	2.64
			·25	·0208	·0081	2.54
			·5	·0196	·0017	1.79
F	600°	8	·125	·0208	·0144	2.56
			·25	·0208	·009	2.36
			·5	·0196	·0022	1.74
G	600°	28	·125	·0208	·0141	2.68
			·25	·0208	·0084	2.48
			·5	·0196	·0015	1.81

TABLE III.

Animal charcoal: activated with nitrogen: atmospheric pressure.

Sample.	Temp. (°C.).	Duration (hrs.).	Amount (g.).	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).	Amount adsorbed (g./mole × 10 ³).
H	600°	4	·125	·0208	·0157	2·04
			·25	·0208	·0104	2·08
			·5	·0196	·0039	1·57
I	600°	24	·125	·0198	·0151	1·88
			·25	·0198	·0097	2·02
			·5	·196	·004	1·56

TABLE IV.

Sugar charcoal: activated with air: pressure 10 mm.

Sample.	Temp. (°C.).	Duration. (hrs.).	Amount. (g.).	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).	Amount adsorbed (g./mole/g × 10 ³).
J	900°	4	·125	·0208	·0191	·68
			·25	·0208	·0186	·44
			·5	·0208	·0175	·33
K	900°	8	·125	·0196	·0196	0
			·25	·0196	·0191	·1
			·5	·0196	·0177	·19
L	900°	24	·125	·0196	·0196	0
			·25	·0196	·0193	·06
			·5	·0196	·0179	·17
M	600°	4	·125	—	—	—
			·25	·0196	·0187	·18
			·5	·0196	·0168	·28
N	600°	8	·125	·0196	·0192	·16
			·25	·0196	·0186	·2
			·5	·0196	·0173	·23

TABLE V.

Sugar charcoal : activated with carbon dioxide : atmospheric pressure.

Sample.	Temp. (°C).	Duration. (hrs.).	Amount. (g.).	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).	Amount adsorbed. (g. mole/g. × 10 ³).
O	900°	4	·125	·0196	·0186	·4
			·25	·0196	·0178	·36
			·5	·0196	·016	·36
P	900°	8	·125	·0196	·0187	·36
			·25	·0196	·0184	·24
			·5	·0196	·0168	·28
Q	900°	24	·125	·0196	·0196	0
			·25	·0196	·0193	·06
			·5	·0196	·0187	·09

TABLE VI.

Gelatin charcoal : activated with air : pressure 10 mm.

Sample.	Temp. (°C).	Duration. (hrs.).	Amount. (g.).	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).	Amount adsorbed (g. mole/g. × 10 ³).
R	600°	4	·125	·0198	·0182	·64
			·25	·0198	·0135	1·24
			·5	·0196	·0184	·12
S	600°	28	·125	·0198	·0188	·40
			·25	·0198	·0173	·50
			·5	·0196	·0183	·13

An increase in the time of activation at first seems to produce an increase in adsorptive power but if the time is longer a decrease results (B and C; E and G; C and D). On the other hand, samples H to S show a uniform decrease in the adsorptive power. This lowering is most marked with sugar charcoal, which acquires a distinctly granular form after activation.

An increase in temperature, the time being kept constant, does not produce a uniform effect. In two cases, viz., with samples A & B and J & M, an increase of temperature causes

an increase in the adsorptive power considerably. K and N however show a decrease in activation with an increase of temperature, the duration of heating being kept at 8 hrs. in this case. Probably in such cases graphitisation sets in.

The indications are that the optimum condition depends on the sample. A higher temperature in some cases compensates for a shorter interval of activation. Carbon dioxide produces on the whole a greater activity. Animal charcoal is decidedly the best adsorbent for the acid. Nitrogen gas appears to have an adverse effect on the adsorptive power of animal charcoal. In Table VII, the order of adsorptive power (decreasing) is given. It will be seen that it depends on the amount of charcoal though the same amount of acid is taken.

TABLE VII.

Amount of Charcoal (g.).	Order of adsorbability.
·125.....	C > G > E > A > F > D > B > H > I > J > R > S, O > P > N > K, L, Q.
·25.....	E > C > G > F > A, B > D > H > I > R > S > J > O > P > N > M > K > L, Q.
·5.....	C, G > E > D > A > F > B > H > I > O > J > M, P > N > L > S > R > Q.

B. *The Anomalous Effect of the Mass of Adsorbent.*

If there be an equilibrium distribution of a solute between the surface of an adsorbent and the solution, the fundamental condition should be satisfied that the amount of adsorption would be a definite function of the activity of the solute in the solution. If the extent of surface per unit mass and the nature of the surface does not change with change of concentration of the solute or there be no substance present on the surface which can distribute itself between the liquid and the interface, then the amount of solute in the surface and that in the solution would vary directly, provided that we are dealing with *positive* adsorption. As the *end concentration* decreases, the amount adsorbed per unit mass should also decrease. Our results show that this condition is not satisfied in several instances and that foreign substances, are present which partake in the distribution between the interface and the solution and also react with the acid. A lower *end concentration* of solute (*cf.* Samples K to N, P to S) produces

greater adsorption per unit mass, when the total mass of the adsorbent increases. Sugar charcoal shows the greatest discrepancy in this respect. Further, this charcoal frequently shows no adsorption, when a small amount (0.125 g.) is taken (K, L, M, Q).

The possible presence of foreign substances is of great interest in view of the contradictory results recorded in the literature. On the assumption that substances which can chemically react with the acid are present and that such reactions (*e.g.*, neutralisation or exchange adsorption) proceed to completion, the amount adsorbed *per unit mass*, calculated as above, should be constant and independent of the end concentration. The results cannot thus be accounted for by such assumptions. It is possible that the surface contains both acidic and basic substances, not necessarily as neutral salts, and that this is responsible for the observed effect of the mass of the charcoal. This calculation is borne out by subsequent observations. It is hoped to deal with this increased adsorption at lower concentration of benzoic acid more in detail in a later communication.

C. *Purification of Activated Charcoal by Washing.*

The importance of the electric charge of the charcoal surface has been indicated in the introduction. The removal of impurities by washing has been followed from conductivity measurements and the resulting changes in the electric charge of the surface has been noted.

Animal Charcoal : The charcoals used in the experiments under this section were all *activated at 600° for 6 hrs., at a reduced pressure of 10 mm. of air.*

Animal charcoal was purified and boiled with conductivity water 8 times. On activation, the resulting charcoal was found to have a negative charge (ash-content 15 per cent.). As previous workers do not record purification of the samples after activation, these were repeatedly boiled with conductivity water. A fall in conductivity, indicating gradual purification, was noticed. After four days, during which the sample was digested 20 times, the animal charcoal was still found to set free detectable amounts of electrolytes. The specific conductivity of the water rose from 0.78×10^{-5} to 1.56×10^{-5} r. o. on being kept in contact with the sample thus obtained.

As a result of this washing the sign of the charge of the charcoal was reversed from negative to positive. The cataphoretic

speeds* (*vide*, Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A** 103, 102) were respectively -117×10^{-5} and $+20 \times 10^{-5}$ cm./sec., under unit potential gradient. The sign indicates the charge of the solid surface. The particles had a considerable velocity of fall and the average of upward and downward movements was taken.

Sugar Charcoal: The charge of sugar charcoal at successive stages of purification was measured by the electro-osmotic method. The finer particles show cataphoresis and this interferes with the accuracy. 15 G. of charcoal were shaken with 500 c. c. conductivity water.

TABLE VIII

Sugar Charcoal.

Name of sample.	I	II	III	IV	V
Sp. conductivity of supernatant liquid (r. o.)	2.4×10^{-5}	$.74 \times 10^{-5}$	$.65 \times 10^{-5}$	$.65 \times 10^{-5}$	$.65 \times 10^{-5}$
Electro-osmotic movement of the bubble in cm. per 3 minutes :	-.2	-.5	-1.45	+.25	+.9

Samples I and II were digested with a limited amount of hot water before activation. They have a negative charge. The conductivity of the supernatant liquid is higher than in the other instances. On further activation of II at 600° (2 hrs.) III was obtained. It shows a lower conductivity but a greater osmosis. The latter observation does not mean a greater negative charge as the size of the particles have to be considered. IV was prepared from III by further digestion and subsequent activation (600° , 6 hrs.). The conductivity of the wash-water for this sample has the same value as in III but the sign of the charge becomes reversed. On further washing this sample, the resulting charcoal V shows a constant conductivity but a greater positive charge. These results show that both on digestion and on activation, the charcoal tends to have a positive charge.

* The suspension remains stable for three hours.

Further experiments on the effect of purification: The following electro-osmotic measurements were carried out at room temperature with charcoal, which was not washed after activation. It has been observed that activation itself results in the partial removal of the electrolytic foreign substances.

TABLE IX.

Sample.	Movement of bubble : (cm. in 3 min.).
Merck's original blood charcoal	- '8
Ditto purified as above but not activated.	+ '14
Ditto purified and activated.	+ '24
Merck's original active carbon.	-1'69
Ditto purified and activated.	+ '8
Sugar charcoal impure (obtained by ignition of cane sugar).	-4'3
Ditto purified and activated.	+1'5
Ditto purified and activated (obtained by dehydration of cane sugar with H ₂ SO ₄).	+2'07
Merck's original animal charcoal.	+1'9
Ditto purified and activated.	+1 1
Gelatin charcoal impure.	-13'0
Ditto purified and activated.	+ '2

In all these instances, on purification or activation, the charcoal acquires a positive charge. This observation is most interesting in view of the statement by Mukherjee (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 219) that "their * charcoal would probably show a positive charge in contact with pure water." It has been stated that the views of Bartell and Miller (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1924, 28, 992) on hydrolytic adsorption by charcoal are similar to those of Mukherjee (*Phil. Mag.*, 1922, 44, 321; also *loc. cit.*). Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) points out that there is an essential difference in detail between the two hypotheses. From Mukherjee's point of view the positive charge of sugar charcoal in contact with water indicates either (i) a preferential primary adsorption of hydrogen ions as compared to hydroxyl ions or (ii) the presence of the cation of a basic oxide on the charcoal

* Bartell and Miller.

surface. The liberation of alkali from sodium chloride, as observed by Miller, is to be ascribed to the displacement of the free hydroxyl ions or anions of weak acids in the liquid side of the interface. The negative charge should be ascribed to the presence of an excess of anions on the surface (solid side of the interface). These anions may be chlorine or fluorine ions present in the preliminary purification or other anions formed on the surface of the charcoal. Traces of ammonia or amino bodies may also be present either from the atmosphere or formed during the process of activation from the nitrogen present. In one case an increase in the p_H of the conductivity water, used for washing a sample of activated sugar charcoal, has been observed (Table XV). The reversal of the charge from negative to positive on washing shows definitely that adsorption of ions (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*) are primarily responsible for the charge of the charcoal surface and it is incapable of an explanation on the basis of Frumkin's theory. Though the negative charge cannot be explained from this theory, the positive charge is in agreement with Frumkin's theory, provided electrokinetic experiments can be assumed to indicate the charge in Frumkin's sense. On the other hand, a negatively charged oxygen charcoal (Kruyt and Kadt, *loc. cit.*) can adsorb alkali and it does not appear that there is any relationship between the electric charge and oxygen potential on the one hand and the charge and acid adsorption on the other in Frumkin's sense.

D. Adsorption of Acids.

Miller (*Technical Bulletin, Agricultural Experiment Station, Michigan State College, 1925, 73, 43*) ascribed the liberation of alkali from salts by sugar charcoal to the capillary activity that is the capacity of the acid to lower the tension of the liquid-solid interface, so that an adsorption of the acid took place analogous to what takes place in a liquid-air interface. This point of view based on the classical theorem of Gibbs is wholly inadequate, as it does not distinguish between the adsorption of an ion or neutral molecule on the solid side of the interface from that on the liquid side (*vide*, Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1929, 49, 362). Besides considerations of capillary activity only lead us to expect liberation of alkali and not of acids. It will be seen later that both acid or alkali can be set free from a neutral salt or adsorbed from their solution (*cf.* Schilow), depending on the condition of preparing the charcoal which definitely goes against this theory.

FIG. 1.
Animal Charcoal (.25 g.).

Nekrassow (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1921, 136, 22, 379; cf. also Dubinin, *loc. cit.*) finds that sugar charcoal exhibits a completely different adsorption of monobasic homologous organic acids in aqueous (also in alcoholic or ethereal) solution, from that shown by animal or blood charcoal. Traube's rule is valid for animal or blood

FIG. 2.

Animal Charcoal (.5 g.).

charcoal but an inversely oriented series is observed for sugar charcoal. He attributed this to a difference in the crystalline structure of the charcoal. Dubinin (*loc. cit.*) obtained other orders of adsorption of such acids by charcoal, prepared from the same source, which were intermediate between these two inverse orders ("mixed series"), depending on the condition of activation. He considers that neither a difference in the structure nor the existence of the oxide B postulated by Schilow (*loc. cit.*) can explain the "mixed series." He ascribes the mixed series to variation in the effective adsorbing surface per unit mass. The latter depends on

the size of the pores and of the molecules of the adsorbate. He also refers to the effect of the formation of the highly active oxide C (Schilow, *loc. cit.*) in inducing a reversal of the order of adsorption of organic acids. It is found however that the formation of the oxide C has not a uniform effect on the acid adsorption, *e.g.*, it does not affect the adsorption of heptylic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Animal and sugar charcoals were prepared as described before. Jena glass bottles were employed and 50 c.c. of the solution were

FIG. 4.

Sugar Charcoal (.5 g.).

used in these experiments. The adsorbent was left in contact with the solution overnight after shaking for 2 hrs. 10 c. c. of the upper liquid were obtained by centrifugal action and titrated by baryta using phenol red as indicator. The concentrations are given in normality and the amount adsorbed in millimoles of the acid. The ash-content of animal charcoal was .15 per cent. and zero for sugar charcoal. Three concentrations, .01, .02 and .04 *N* were used. The results are given in the graphs (Fig. 1 to 4).

The continuous increase of the amount adsorbed with concentration and the tendency for the adsorbed amount to rise to a maximum (Fig. 1 to 4) disappears (Fig. 5 and 6) on plotting the results with different amounts of adsorbent in a single curve. This is very significant and shows that experiments with a constant mass of adsorbent (and constant volume of adsorbate) do not suffice as evidence of adsorption equilibrium between a *pure* adsorbent and a solute.

The order of adsorption of the acids brings out certain interesting features. In Table X the first, second and third columns give the decreasing order of adsorption of acids by animal charcoal (.5, .25 and .125 g. respectively), while the fourth, fifth and sixth columns give the orders with sugar charcoal, The seventh column shows the order of adsorption by blood charcoal (as given by Freundlich in *Colloid and Capillary Chemistry*, Eng. Ed., 1926. p. 198); the eighth by Fromageot (*Compt. rend.*, 1924, 179, 972); the ninth gives the

FIG. 5.

Animal Charcoal.

Symbol 1 corresponds to .125 g. of charcoal.
 „ 2 „ .25 g. „ „
 „ 3 „ .5 g. „ „

order of dissociation constants of the acids (Kohlrausch und Holborn, Das Leitvermögen Der Elektrolyte, 1916, p. 186) and the last that of

FIG. 6.
Sugar Charcoal.

Symbol 1 corresponds to .125 g. of charcoal.

„ 2 „ .25 g. „ „

„ 3 „ .5 g. „ „

solubilities (Seidell, Solubilities of Inorganic and Organic Compounds, 1919). The numerals are explained below:—

- (1) Benzoic, (2) oxalic, (3) butyric, (4) monochloroacetic,
(5) dichloroacetic, (6) propionic, (7) acetic, (8) formic,
and (9) trichloroacetic.

TABLE X.

(1)* ·01N ·02N ·04N		(2)* ·01N ·02N ·04N		(3)* ·02N	(4)* ·01N ·02N ·04N		(5)* ·01N ·02N ·04N		(6)* ·02N	(7)**	(8)**	(9)*·	(10)*·
1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	7	1	2	(3.0×10^{-1}) ⁹	7
3	3	3	2	{ 5	4	4	{ 2	{ 8	4	3	6	(3.8×10^{-2}) ²	9
2	4	{ 2	3	{ 4	6	{ 6	{ 4	{	6	4	8	(5.1×10^{-2}) ⁵	4
6	{ 5	{ 4	4	7	8	{ 7	{ 6	{ 3	1	5	7	(1.55×10^{-3}) ⁴	2
5	{ 6	{ 5	5	6	{ 7	{ 8	{ 8	{ 7	5	9		(2.14×10^{-4}) ⁸	1
4	2	{ 6	{ 6	9	3	1	1	6	9	6		(6.0×10^{-5}) ¹	
7	7	{ 7	{ 7	{ 1	1	5	5	1	1			(1.8×10^{-5}) ⁷	
9	9	{ 8	{ 8	{ 5	3	3	3	5	5			(1.5×10^{-5}) ³	
8	8	{ 9	{ 9	9	9	9	9	9	9			(1.3×10^{-5}) ⁶	

* At 23°-25°. ** At 25°. † First dissociation constant.

The order depends on the mass of the adsorbent and is different for the two samples. Freundlich's order for blood charcoal* is the same (excepting trichloroacetic acid) as that observed here with animal charcoal.* Fromageot's order of acid adsorption agrees approximately with the order obtained by us with sugar charcoal.

On examination of the individual results for the *animal charcoal*, oxalic acid shows the greatest irregularity and mono- and dichloroacetic acids to a much smaller extent. Barring these acids the order of adsorption by animal charcoal is as follows:—

Benzoic > butyric > propionic > acetic > formic > trichloroacetic. The curves for the pairs, formic & trichloroacetic and mono- & dichloroacetic, intersect each other. Assuming Freundlich's isotherm to hold good, it indicates that the two constants in the equation (α and β) are different for each of these pairs. The actual amount of its adsorption is almost the same with .5 and .25 g., though that calculated per unit mass when .25 g. is used is double of that when .5 g. is used. This observation makes it likely that equilibrium relations are not obtained with this acid. With sugar charcoal, oxalic acid again shows the greatest irregularity which is also the case though to a less extent with acetic, propionic and butyric acids. The two curves for different amounts of adsorbent have altogether dissimilar forms. It is difficult to speak of a definite order of adsorption independent of concentration.

Sugar and animal charcoals show a marked contrast. With the former, oxalic acid is most adsorbed, whereas benzoic acid takes the precedence in the case of the latter. Animal charcoal has on the whole, a greater adsorptive power than sugar charcoal. The irregularity with mono- and dichloroacetic acids observed with animal charcoal is not observed with sugar charcoal, whereas the reverse occurs with acetic, propionic and butyric acids. The latter acids were Merck's extra pure and used without further purification. The irregularities with oxalic acid (animal charcoal) and acetic acid (sugar charcoal) are most marked. The adsorption of the four homologous aliphatic acids, formic, acetic, propionic and butyric by animal charcoal follows Traube's rule (Fig. 1 and

* Blood charcoal, as is known, contains a considerable percentage of iron and animal charcoal calcium, along with other impurities but the percentage of ash is different.

2). With sugar charcoal (Fig. 3 and 4) there is no definite order and Traube's rule fails for acetic, propionic and butyric acids (*cf.* Nekrassow, *loc. cit.*). The order of adsorption of the three chloroacetic acids is the same in all cases, and agrees with their capillary activity (Freundlich, *Colloid and Capillary Chemistry*, p. 197).

It is difficult to say how far these differences result from the amount and nature of foreign substances or from differences in the size of the pores and of the adsorbed molecules or ions as suggested by Dubinin (*loc. cit.*). It is thus obvious from the work of Schilow, Dubinin and others and the present one, that the removal of acids from solution by activated charcoal does not admit of a simple explanation and is a very complicated process. The simplest possible explanation would be to ascribe the want of any regularity to the formation of different types of compounds (not merely oxides of carbon) during activation.

These observations also show that the order of adsorption of the different acids bear no relation to the order of solubilities (Bartell and Ying Fu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 686).

E. Equivalent Adsorption of both Ions of Acids.

The equivalent adsorption of ions of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids observed by previous workers (Miller, *loc. cit.*, Kolthoff, *loc. cit.*) has been confirmed. Duplicate experiments were carried out. The total acidity was determined by titration and the chloride and sulphate estimated gravimetrically. 75 C.c. of solution were taken and concentrations are given in normality.

TABLE XI.

Hydrochloric Acid: Initial total acid conc. = 0.193N.

Amount (g.).	Final conc. total acid (N).	C_{Cl} total chlorine conc. (N).
1	0.174	0.177
"	0.178	0.178
2	0.160	0.158
"	0.160	0.162

TABLE XII.

Sulphuric Acid: Initial total acid conc. = 0.0204N.

Amount (g.).	Final conc. total acid (N).	Total sulphate conc. (N).
1	0.02	0.0203
„	0.02	
2	0.0193	0.0192
„	0.0194	

It will be shown later from electro-osmotic experiments that excess adsorption of chlorine, hydrogen, hydroxyl and sulphate ions cannot be doubted. Obviously the assumption that equivalent adsorption of ions of an electrolyte, as obtained from analytical data, signifies *molecular* adsorption (that is, adsorption of neutral undissociated molecules of acids) is erroneous (*cf.* Fromageot, as also Phelps and Peters, *loc. cit.*). The total amounts of either ions present in the interface may be equivalent but the presence of one in excess on the solid side of the interface is responsible for the electro-kinetic potential drop in it.

F. *Effect of Ethyl Alcohol on the Adsorption of Acids by Different Samples of Charcoal.*

0.5 G. of the charcoal and 100 c.c. benzoic acid (0.01 N) containing different percentages of ethyl alcohol were shaken and kept overnight.

TABLE XIII.

Charcoal.	Ethyl alcohol.	Final conc. (N).	Amount of acid adsorbed (g. mole/g. × 10 ³).
Blood charcoal (Merck's)	0	0.0041	1.92
	1	0.00456	1.91
	5	0.00593	1.88
	10	0.0091	1.82

Charcoal.	Ethyl alcohol.	Final conc. (N).	Amount of acid adsorbed (g. mole/g. $\times 10^3$).
Active carbon (Merck's)	0	.00273	1.45
	1	.00301	1.40
	5	.00356	1.29
	10	.00419	1.18
Sugar charcoal (activ- ated and purified)	0	.00923	.15
	1	.00968	.064
	5	.00968	.064
	10	.00968	.064
Animal charcoal (activ- ated and purified)	0	.00225	1.55
	1	.00248	1.50
	5	.00315	1.37
	10	.00383	1.23

Michaelis considers that (Freundlich, *Colloid and Capillary Chemistry, loc. cit.*) non-electrolytes can displace neutral molecules of electrolytes but not the ions individually. Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) also holds that capillary-active non-electrolytes can displace strong acids. In the present case, the formation of esters is not likely and the decrease in adsorption with the concentration of alcohol observed with *active carbon* and animal charcoal indicates the displacement of the adsorption of the acid. This observation is consistent with the higher capillary activity of alcohol, assuming that the surface tension changes in an air-liquid interface are parallel to those of a solid-liquid interface, where the liquid is the same. The results however do not show a uniform effect of the concentration of the alcohol and depend on the sample used. It is necessary to point out also that such consideration of capillary activity on the basis of Gibb's theory of adsorption and deduced from analytical measurements overlooks the distribution of the ions between the solid and the liquid side of the interface and is of no value in deciding whether the adsorption is *molecular* (*i.e.*, of undissociated molecules) or ionic.

G. *Hydrolytic Adsorption and Electrical Charge of the Charcoal Surface.*

The charcoal was prepared, purified, activated and preserved, as previously described (600°, 6 hrs.). The charcoal and the solution were kept in Jena glass bottles overnight after the mixture has been well shaken. The upper liquid obtained with the help of a centrifuge was titrated. Its p^H was also measured by an indicator set. The concentrations of electrolytes in the following tables are given in normality ;

Electro-osmotic Experiments: Carried out as described in section C.

TABLE XIV.

5 G. of charcoal was treated with 50 c.c. of electrolyte.

Sample I. Animal charcoal: negatively charged (ash·15%).

Electrolyte.	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).
HCl	·01	·01
KOH	·01	·007
KCl	·01	·0086(acid)

Sample II. Purified Animal charcoal*: positively charged (ash·15%).

HCl	·0097	·00824
KOH	·0097	·00756
KCl	·0097	(Neutral)
KCl	·00485	(Neutral)

* This sample contained 74·2% water. In weighing the charcoal and in calculating the initial concentration of electrolyte added, the necessary correction was made.

TABLE XV.

Sugar charcoal: positively charged (ash-0 %)—Sample A.

Volume of Electrolyte = 50 c.c.

Electrolyte.	Amount of charcoal (g.).	Final conc. (N.)	Titre (c.c.) of .02 N-HCl or —KOH for 10 c.c. of soln. after adsorption.	Final Conc. (N) & pH.
Water (pH, 6.8)	.125	—		7.2 pH
	.25	—		7.2
KCl (pH, 6.7)	.125	.02	—	7.9
	.25	.02	—	7.9
KCl (pH, 6.7)	.125	.01	—	7.9
	.25	.01	—	7.9
HCl	.125	.02	9.5	.0196 N
	.25	.02	9.45	.0189
HCl	.125	.01	4.8	.0096
	.25	.01	4.65	.0093
CH ₃ COOH	.125	.02	9.15	.0183
	.25	.02	8.35	.0167
CH ₃ COOK (pH, 7.0)	.125	.02	—	7.9 pH
	.25	.02	—	7.9
CH ₃ COOK (pH, 7.1)	.125	.01	—	7.7
	.25	.01	—	7.7
KOH	.125	.02	10	.02 N
	.25	.02	10	.02

TABLE XVI.

Effect of the Addition of Neutral Electrolytes on the Adsorption of Hydrochloric Acid.

Sugar charcoal: positively charged—Sample B.

.5 G. charcoal + 100 c.c. solution.

Solution.	Initial acidity. (pH) 6.7	Acidity after contact with charcoal. (pH) 6.7	Amount absorbed (g. mole./g. × 10 ³).
Water			—
.01 N-KCl	„ 6.7	„ 6.9	—
.01 N-BaCl ₂	„ 6.6	„ 6.8	—
.01 N-HCl	.01 N	.00952 N	.096
.01 N-HCl + .01 N-KCl	.01 N	.00952 N	.096
.01 N-HCl + .01 N-BaCl ₂	.01 N	.00952 N	.096

Effect of Electrolytes on the Charge of Different Samples of Charcoal.

The following samples were obtained by activation after purification as usual.

TABLE XVII.

(Sugar charcoal : ash-negligible).

Concentrations.	Movement of bubble.			
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	NaOH*	
	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 1
0	+ 1·5	+ 1·3	+ ·13	+ ·9
·0001N	- ·25	- ·35	- ·1	- ·25
·0002N	- ·25	- ·4	- ·45	- ·38
·001N	+ 1·0	+ ·78	- 3·0	- ·91

TABLE XVIII.

Movement of bubble.

Concentrations.	Animal charcoal : ash·15 per cent.			Blood charcoal : ash·31 per cent.	
	HCl	NaOH		HCl	H ₂ SO ₄
	Sample 1	Sample 1	Sample 2		
0	+ 1·08	+ ·81	+ ·76	+ 2·1	+ 2·1
·0001N	+ 2·35	+ 2·15	+ 1·85	—	—
·0002N	+ 4·75	+ 1·7	+ 2·23	+ 4·0	+ 2·54
·001N	+ 1·4	+ 1·16	—	+ 1·5	+ 1·91
·008N	—	- ·99	- 4·8	—	—

TABLE XIX.

Movement of bubble.

Concentrations.	Merck's activated carbon : ash-7·5 per cent.		Gelatin charcoal : ash-6·2 per cent.
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	
0	+ ·8	+ ·2	
·0001N	+ 1·16	—	
·0002 N	+ 3 1	- ·45	
·001 N	—	- 1·15	
·008 N	+ 5·2	—	

* The adsorption of atmospheric carbon dioxide should be taken into consideration in interpreting the results.

The negatively charged animal charcoal does not adsorb acid but adsorbs alkali. In contact with potassium chloride, it liberates acid. The above sample, if further purified by washing, adsorbs more acid and less alkali; also no free acid or alkali (as measured by titration) is liberated from potassium chloride. Sugar charcoal adsorbs acid but not alkali; it liberates alkali from neutral potassium chloride. The absorption of acid from potassium chloride and the pH of the wash-water depend on the sample (A, B).

Sample 'A' definitely contains traces of an alkaline substance. In section B, it has been pointed out that this charcoal contains impurities possibly of an alkaline nature. The adsorption of acid is also smaller with 'B.' Neutral chlorides have no effect on the adsorption of hydrochloric acid. From an examination of the data (Section A), it will be evident that the irregular effect of the mass of the adsorbent is absent with animal charcoal, when activated after the usual purification with carbon dioxide (Section A, Tables I and II). When however nitrogen is used (Table III), a greater adsorption than that indicated by the equilibrium concentration of the acid is observed, when the mass of the adsorbent is increased. This observation is also in agreement with the assumed presence of alkaline substances. Animal charcoal differs from sugar charcoal in this regard. The initial negative charge as also the fact that after washing the acid adsorption increases, the alkali adsorption decreases and the charge becomes positive, point to the presence of acidic impurities in the negatively charged animal charcoal. The primary adsorption of anions is further supported by the observation that Merck's animal charcoal (from which our samples of animal charcoal have been prepared), is positively charged (Table IX) but after treatment with acids and preliminary washing, it acquires a negative charge and becomes positive only on further careful purification, (Section I). Moreover, positive animal charcoal adsorbs benzoic acid more than the negative does.

TABLE XX.

100 C.c. of benzoic acid taken: time of contact = 20 hrs.

Amount of charcoal taken = .25 g.

Sample.	Initial conc. (N).	Final conc. (N).	Amount adsorbed (g. mole/g. $\times 10^3$).
Negatively charged animal charcoal	.021	.0178	1.28
Positively charged animal charcoal	.0107	.015	2.28

It is thus clear that contrary to Schilow's postulates, the excess adsorption (primary) of both cations and anions of the solid side of the interface has to be taken into account.

Sugar charcoal.—Positively charged sugar charcoal (Table XVII) becomes negatively charged in presence of very low concentrations of hydrochloric acid. It becomes again positive at higher concentrations. With sulphuric acid and sodium hydroxide, the charge remains negative within the same range of concentration. That the solid side of the interface can react with hydrogen, hydroxyl, sulphate and chlorine ions is established by these results and distribution of ions in Mukherjee's sense (*loc. cit.*) has to be taken into account. The conception of the formation of an ionogen complex (Pauli and Valko, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, 121, 161, also Pennycuik, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 1447) suffers from an obvious defect though commonly overlooked. The formation of an ionogen complex does not explain why one part of it (a component ion of the complex) will remain fixed on the solid surface and the other in the mobile sheet of the double layer. The initial positive charge followed by a negative and then a positive charge (sugar charcoal and hydrochloric acid) show clearly that attention should be focussed on the fixation. Also the conclusion of Phelps and Peters (*loc. cit.*) and of Fromageot (*loc. cit.*) that charcoal selectively adsorbs non-dissociated molecules of acids and not ions are not borne out by the above.

Ogawa (*loc. cit.*) found that sugar charcoal treated with acid becomes positively charged and when treated with alkali is negatively charged. Our results confirm this. Also Miller's observation (*loc. cit.*) that sodium hydroxide is not adsorbed by purified sugar charcoal is confirmed. Miller and Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) have sometimes observed negative adsorption of the alkali.

The enhancing effect of sodium hydroxide on the negative charge (Table XVII) indicates two possibilities: (i) the adsorbed cations present in the solid side of the interface are partially displaced by ions in the mobile layer so as to increase the free negative charge, (ii) the increase is due to the primary adsorption of hydroxyl ions either as such or as forming anions with electrolytes present in the surface. The absence of adsorption of sodium hydroxide together with the negative adsorption of alkali recorded in some instances (*loc. cit.*) may be best reconciled as indicating presence of basic salts. With higher temperature of activation, there is a marked fall in the amount of adsorption (Section A; see also Frumkin and

Schilow, *loc. cit.*). It may indicate loss of the electrolytes present on the surface.

The high adsorptive capacity of sample J (Section B), which was heated for 4 hrs. at 900° , indicates however that the presence of impurities of a basic nature is not the only factor determining the adsorption. In this instance the adsorption does not depend on the mass as in the other cases and increases regularly with the equilibrium concentration of the acid and at the same time the adsorption is quite marked. The nature of the charcoal surface is a factor which has to be taken into account. We also conclude that activated sugar charcoal prepared after Miller (*loc. cit.*) possibly contains removable impurities.

Animal, Blood and Gelatin Charcoal and Merck's Active Carbon (purified and activated as usual).—These charcoals contain an appreciable percentage of ash. It is not surprising that they behave differently in contact with electrolytes. They all become positively charged with hydrochloric acid and do not show the negative charge at low concentrations of the acid observed with sugar charcoal. Both animal and blood charcoals (ash-content— $\cdot 15\%$ and $\cdot 31\%$ respectively) show a diminution of the positive charge at $\cdot 301N$. With the charcoal obtained from Merck's active carbon, which has a higher ash-content ($7\cdot 5\%$), the positive charge increases even at $\cdot 008N$. The amount and the nature of the inorganic substances probably play a very important part. The samples behave as complex systems and have different properties.

With sulphuric acid (Tables XVII, XVIII and XIX), sugar and gelatin charcoals show a similarity in the results but a contrast to blood charcoal, though the gelatin charcoal contains $6\cdot 2\%$ ash and sugar charcoal is practically free from it. This again shows that the ash-content is not the only factor. The manner of activation has a definite influence. It is probably the determining factor, so far as the organic impurities and the structure of the surface are concerned. The nature of the inorganic as also perhaps of the organic impurities and the structure of the solid side of the interface should also be considered.

With sodium hydroxide, animal charcoal (Table XVIII) shows an increase in the positive charge and becomes negative only at $\cdot 008N$. The initial increase in the positive charge is consistent with the assumption of the presence of cations and anions on the surface. It

indicates that the anions combine with the alkali and pass out of the interface. At higher concentration, the adsorption of hydroxyl ions or of the anions formed in the above manner diminishes the positive charge and makes it ultimately negative. Umetsu (*loc. cit.*) made the following observations: (a) blood charcoal has a negative charge in moderate dilution of sodium hydroxide ($\cdot 01N$); it is negatively charged in rather dilute hydrochloric acid solution (up to $\cdot 00145N$) and in the more concentrated acid solution the charge becomes positive. With sulphuric acid, it has a negative charge up to $\cdot 00143N$ and a positive at higher concentrations. (b) Sugar charcoal was however found to have a negative charge throughout the same range of concentrations of hydrochloric acid. He used Merck's blood charcoal, which we find to be negatively charged and which becomes positive on purification.

Ogawa (*loc. cit.*) working with normal and activated sugar charcoal (ash-free) records that the latter has no charge (iso-electric) in $\cdot 002N$ sodium hydroxide solution and negative in $\cdot 02N$. In neutral ($\cdot 02N$ -KCl solution) and hydrochloric acid solutions ($\cdot 02N$ and $\cdot 002N$), the charge was found to be positive. There are no data at other concentrations or in contact with pure water. His observations are in agreement with our results (Table XVII), in so far as the behaviour at higher concentrations of HCl and NaOH are concerned. In dilute acid and alkali concentrations ($\cdot 001N$ and $\cdot 0002N$), it is negatively charged and in these respects the results are different from those observed by Ogawa.

Neither Umetsu nor Ogawa observed however the two-fold reversal in the sign of the charge of sugar charcoal from positive to negative at low concentrations and from negative to positive at high concentrations with hydrochloric acid (Table XVII). The above differences show again that inorganic substances are not alone responsible for the different properties of charcoal as both samples are free from ash-

The preceding observations establish clearly that the nature of the electrolytic impurities, of the electric charge and the hydrolytic adsorption are correlated and in fact, in a manner which is in accord with the postulates of Mukherjee. As stated before, considerations of interfacial tension overlook the manner of distribution of ions in the interface. Apart from this, it cannot account for (a) the variations of charge on washing, (b) the relation between the charge and

the adsorbabilities of acid and alkali and (c) the role of the charge in determining whether hydrolytic adsorption results in liberation of acid or alkali and (d) the dependence of the charge on impurities.

The adsorption of acid and alkali and hydrolytic adsorption in relation to the theories referred to in the introduction will be further dealt with in the second part.

Summary.

1. Reference has been made in the introduction to the important role, which the electric charge of adsorbent plays in adsorption processes. The theories of Frumkin and Schilow have been criticised in the light of recent experimental data of Dubinin, Kruyt and also of the author and of Mukherjee and co-workers.

2. An anomalous effect of mass of charcoal, obtained from different sources and activated under different conditions, on the absorption of benzoic acid has been examined. The presence of substances other than carbon on the surface of the charcoal is indicated. The amount and nature of these foreign substances depend on the conditions of activation. Sometimes a lower end-concentration of solute has been found to produce greater adsorption per unit mass, when the total mass of the adsorbent increases and sugar charcoal has been found to show the greatest discrepancy in this respect. The result cannot be explained by an adsorption equilibrium or by neutralisation process and indicate that complicated processes are at work.

3. All samples of charcoal after careful purification and washing have been found to acquire a positive charge in contact with water. From Mukherjee's point of view, pure charcoal in contact with water should acquire a positive charge due to preferential primary adsorption of hydrogen ions as compared to hydroxyl ions or basic cations present in the charcoal. The initial negative charge observed with some samples should be ascribed to the presence of an excess of anions on the surface (solid side of the interface). Traces of ammonia or amino bodies may be present either from the atmosphere or formed during the process of activation from the nitrogen present.

4. The order of adsorption of organic acids by charcoal has been found to be different for different samples. The adsorption curves intersect each other in some cases. The curves for different amounts of the same sample have altogether dissimilar forms. The order cannot be explained by *capillary activity* or from chemical considerations such as the dissociation constant or the solubility. The orders of adsorption resemble the *mixed series* observed by Dubinin, with this difference that the order depends also on the amount of the adsorbent. This latter observation cannot be accounted for by considerations of available pore space advanced by Dubinin for the *mixed series*. It cannot also be due to the formations of the oxides A, B or C as postulated by Schilow, as the observations show that there is scarcely any regularity as to the formation of different types of compounds on the surface of the charcoal.

5. The equivalent adsorption of the anion and the cation of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids found by previous workers has been confirmed. It has been pointed out that the assumption that equivalent adsorption of ions of an electrolyte as obtained from analytical data signifies *molecular* adsorption is erroneous.

6. Ethyl alcohol decreases the adsorption of benzoic acid but the results depend on the sample used.

7. Negatively charged animal charcoal adsorbs only alkali and not acid, positively charged animal charcoal adsorbs both acid and alkali.

8. Activated sugar charcoal adsorbs only acid and not alkali. Neutral solution in contact with sugar charcoal becomes alkaline. This confirms the observation of Bartell and Miller.

9. Measurements of charge of sugar charcoal in contact with acid and alkali solutions indicate that the condition in the solid side of the interface has to be distinguished from that in the liquid side. The adsorption of ions of one sign in excess on the solid side is clearly demonstrated. OH' , H' , Cl' and SO_4'' ions can be adsorbed on the solid side.

It gives me great pleasure to express my thanks to Prof. J. N. Mukherjee for suggesting this work and for facilities. I am also thankful to the authorities of the University of Calcutta

for awarding me a research scholarship, which has enabled me to undertake this work.

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE
AND TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received January, 1, 1931.

Addenda (August, 3, 1931.)

The following papers having a bearing on the present communication have since been published. It is proposed to deal with these in a subsequent communication. Bruns, *Kolloid Z.*, 1931, 54, 33; *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 155, 77; Frumkin, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1931, 155, 41; Kruyt, *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1931, 32, 249.

